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CONTENTS

Executive Summary	4
<i>Goals.....</i>	4
<i>Main outcome</i>	4
Introduction	6
RESULTS: WP9 Co-creation platform	7
Baseline for competitiveness – Icelandic stakeholders and world café	7
Crisis and Adaption – Expert Perspectives on the German Aquaculture.	
Stakeholder meeting “Shape Aquaculture!”	8
Competitiveness and Sustainable Sourcing in Europe for Fish and Seafood.	12
Price Transmission and Market Power in the Seafood Value Chain in Europe:	14
SUCCESS Co-creation platform and Case Study on Coastal Fisheries.....	17
Mussel farming in Italy - opportunities for growth and valorisation.....	20
WORKSHOP ON BLUE GROWTH: SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF THE FISHERY & AQUACULTURE SECTOR.....	22
Future Trade in Seafood - SUCCESS Co-creation platform.....	27
The Seafood Conference Iceland 2017,	33
STAKEHOLDERS’ PERCEPTION OF SUSTAINABILITY,	34
References.....	38
ANNEX I – News Clippings from events.....	40

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The outcomes from the various stakeholder consultations carried out by the SUCCESS project, and by a final round of focus group meetings were used to prepare this report on preferred sustainable market solutions and an indicative roadmap for implementation of SUCCESS outcomes as perceived by the stakeholders. This includes assessments of impact potential for varying measures and tools developed by the SUCCESS work-packages to present both stakeholder perspectives and the SUCCESS scientific outcomes. This report is delivered as a public summary of the findings from the co-creation work involving stakeholders in the SUCCESS project.

GOALS

The goals were to facilitate the building of a co-creation and stakeholder platform to engage various value chain stakeholders in participatory manner and interactions with the SUCCESS partners. Through this enable targeted consulting actions (e.g. workshops, focus groups) with relevant actors like the fishermen, aquaculture producers and their associations, and to engage value chain operators driving the market interactions between primary producers, sellers and the consumers,

This activity was used to elucidate through consultations with the seafood supply chain stakeholders their concerns, perceptions and how to adopt this guidance into the research work throughout the SUCCESS project.

The goal was to develop and mobilise existing marketing tools valued by stakeholders for being suitable for enhancing consumer trust and healthy choices of seafood's and deliver outputs to focus SUCCESS project dissemination and outreach actions that have a potential in positively influence and steer European consumer choices.

MAIN OUTCOME

The stakeholder inputs and opinions varied somewhat across themes being addressed by the events and activities, however, often a consistent consensus and resonance of common opinions regarding room for improvement and how to progress. Example of this would be that for aquaculture licensing, the barrier created by having numerous national agencies and complex regulatory frameworks was considered to severely restrict sector growth opportunities across Europe. Another example showing similar consensus was on sustainability labelling measures, as these were considered able to provide positive market opportunities for short regional supply chains. On the other hand, the sustainability labels demanded by the large retailers were considered as necessary "must-have" to be able to enter certain markets, and in many cases placed burden and costs on the producers that in the long run would be transferred to the consumers. Linked to this, the consumer surveys showed definite signs of label-fatigue and that consumers were often not sure what the labels really meant.

Overall the results of the co-creation activities have been used as inputs into several deliverable reports from the SUCCESS project, like e.g. D5.3 a public report titled "*Recommendation for the development of strategies and policies for EU fishing industry and aquaculture*". The policy options developed represent research results as well from the case studies and identified room for improvements. The summary below lists some key outcomes addressed, and for further details refer also to the reviews presented in chapter 2 of this report that were produced from individual stakeholder events and actions.

Following is a list of selected sustainable market perspectives from the SUCCESS co-creation work with stakeholders:

1. Different cultural perspectives exist that may motivate stakeholders differently across Europe, i.e. North vs. South European perspectives, and also differences arising from the Common Fishery Policy (CFP) vs. elsewhere in Europe not covered by the CFP.
2. Many policy options must be assessed at the individual case study level (due to heterogeneity).
3. Data collection improvement is considered important (for e.g. labour, capital structure/lack of market oriented and environmental indicators, and more disaggregated data is needed).

4. Technical efficiency is considered important for improving environmentally friendly fishing methods.
5. Imperative to simplify and improve legal frameworks and regulations, e.g. to reduce conflicts between short term and long term issues and overlap of local regional, national, EU terms of reference.
6. Environmental regulation clarity improvement needed, and better information basis required with focus on spatial management considerations, especially in aquaculture.
 - Consider if ecosystem services provided by e.g. carp aquaculture could be promoted as part of Natura and tourism.
7. Labelling for sustainability, origin and quality schemes remains a complicated issue, resulting in label fatigue, consumer segmentation and country differences that can provide negative or positive impacts.
 - Impacts direction relies on informing consumers properly for informed choices, and implementing measures targeting, or supporting Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) to provide transparent information for increasing ocean literacy,
 - Such efforts are also considered important at municipality levels, as well as regional and on EU wide level.
8. Producer Organisations and Cooperatives should be promoted
 - Provide incentives and opportunities through EU legislation, e.g. through allocation of user rights,
 - Value chain and market bargain power promotion through measures like business concentration, both via vertical and horizontal integration,
 - Promote initiatives by SMEs on training.
9. The CFP discard ban will require more work on quota allocation modelling to underpin the optimal way forward for the sector.
10. Promote further energy saving technologies and consider a ban on fuel subsidies for the fishing sector.
11. Promote further work on new products and product differentiation measures (like e.g. the Greece and Trapani mussels label, direct-selling and short supply chains etc.).

INTRODUCTION

The stakeholder co-creation activities organized by the SUCCESS project were carried out through several stakeholder workshops, focus groups, surveys and participation in events that brought the consortium partners into dialogue with relevant sector stakeholders, and policy agents. The events addressed selection of themes, where SUCCESS project participants interacted with selected representative stakeholders in a co-creation work relevant to achieve the core project outcomes. The main co-creation SUCCESS workshop events are listed below:

- Stakeholder event in Malta 4-5 February 2016. Session and interventions during the Conference on economic advice in fisheries management, hosted by DG Mare¹
- *World Café “Baseline for competitiveness”, Reykjavik, 12 April 2016*
- *Stakeholder meeting “Shape Aquaculture!” 14 April 2016, Thünen Institutes of Fisheries Ecology and Sea Fisheries in Hamburg*
- *Focus Group Workshop and World Café, Rome, May 18-19, 2016, “Competitiveness and Sustainable Sourcing in Europe for Fish and Seafood”*
- *Non-tariff measures (NTM) industry focus group in Hamburg, 29 November 2016.*
- *Stakeholders' perception analysis, World Café, Santander, May 10-12, 2017. Price Transmission and Market Power in the Seafood Value Chain in Europe*
- *Slow Fish International event Genova, 18-21 May 2017, focused on the case study on coastal fisheries and included a survey questionnaire*
- *Workshop Cattolica, ITALY – 29 May. 2017. Mussel farming in Italy: opportunities for growth and valorisation*
- *Workshop on Blue Growth: Sustainable Development of the Fishery and Aquaculture Sector, 7-8th September 2017 - SANTANDER (Spain)*
- *Workshop and World Café on NTMs, Brussels, Belgium 10-11 October 2017*
- *The Seafood Conference Iceland, 15-16 November 2017, a booth showcasing SUCCESS project,*
 - *STAKEHOLDERS' PERCEPTION OF SUSTAINABILITY, On-line survey conducted in November 2017 in connection with the Seafood Conference Iceland.*

In addition to the workshop events listed above, surveys were conducted to gain insights and inputs into stakeholder perceptions on the issues concerning them in relation to the seafood and aquaculture sectors. Number of other actions involving stakeholders were managed by SUCCESS partners in connection with their case study² research work and the results of this is not covered by this report.

¹ More information on the event website, visited by internet in March 2018, <http://economics-fisheries.eu/programme.html>

² Visit SUCCESS website for information on all project workshops, by Internet in March 2018; <http://www.success-h2020.eu/success-workshops/>

- ⇒ Prevent misunderstanding about content of certifications on sustainability (economic, environmental and social)
- Certification according to standards builds trust, and is sometimes a zero point or a baseline, which creates new opportunities. The uptake of voluntary standards opens markets opportunities and they motivate progress when implementing new requirements
- Marketing and image building are based on telling a good story! The fish industry in Iceland is competitive and successful
 - ⇒ The good stories are on e.g. sustainable sourcing, fisheries management, high quality of products, innovation, traceability, certification against standards and social responsibility
- Social media is an opportunity to reach out to the new generation of consumers. The younger generation trusts this form of communication and there are opportunities to develop and adapt consumer apps and social media for marketing of fish.

CRISIS AND ADAPTION – EXPERT PERSPECTIVES ON THE GERMAN AQUACULTURE. STAKEHOLDER MEETING “SHAPE AQUACULTURE!”

Thünen Institutes of Fisheries Ecology and Sea Fisheries in Hamburg, April 14th, 2016

The objective was to synergise approaches of the European fisheries and aquaculture research, SUCCESS⁶ partners have been working closely together with the EU Horizon 2020 sister projects AquaSpace⁷ and CERES⁸ in preparation of the stakeholder meeting. A quoted sample of 22 stakeholders, which work in the business sector, in national or federal states politics, in county administrations or environmental protection were selected. All 22 invitees have in common, that they have an expert knowledge regarding aquaculture. Further, all experts participated have in common that they deal with marine and/or freshwater aquaculture in their day-today work. The experts were chosen as representatives of an institution and opinion leader. For discussion, the experts were distributed across three smaller focus groups. Each focus group consisted of 7-8 experts. Each field of expertise mentioned above was represented in each focus group. The discussion started with a stimulus set by the moderator:

“Aquaculture can be seen as international success story. Indeed, within the EU strategy „Blue Growth“, high expectations towards aquaculture are formulated. In Germany, the sector is comparable small and diverse. The development of the German sector has been stagnating for many years. Today, 90 % of German aquatic products are imported. Some people say, there is no need for a domestic aquaculture in Germany. What do you think?”

After setting the stimulus, the experts started the discussion almost self-regulated. The moderator did not control the focus group in their discussion. This open-inductive procedure is a core principle of qualitative social research, which allows to gather the expert's interpretation of a situation. After ca. 60 minutes, the moderator asked two further questions, one addressing factors hampering the growth of aquaculture and one pointing to assumed climate change impacts towards aquaculture. Those questions have been chosen to meet all objectives of the abovementioned research projects, even if the expert would not touch these topics by themselves. Indeed, all three focus groups discussed factors which hamper the aquaculture growth in Germany without extra setting up the question, but only one group discussed the topic of climate change without the introduction of this topic by the moderator.

⁶ Strategic Use of Competitiveness towards Consolidating the Economic Sustainability of the European Seafood sector (Grant No 635188); <http://www.success-h2020.eu/>

⁷ Ecosystem Approach to making Space for Aquaculture (Grant No 633476); <http://www.aquaspace-h2020.eu/>

⁸ Climate change and European aquatic RESources (Grant No 678193); <http://ceresproject.eu/>

The focus groups have been recorded under the agreement that the results will be published anonymized.

In the following table the contents addressed by the focus groups are listed in alphabetical order. The summarized contents can be contradictory.

The contents of the discussions are summarized and categorized as followed: authorization and obligations, company organization, consumer behaviour, differentiation, federalism, location factors, image, predators and climate change. Further, they are divided by dimensions of crisis and adaption. From a sociological point of view, a crisis is defined as a situation perceived as problematic, which cannot be solved via established actions or strategies⁹.

Adaption is a strategy to overcome a problematic situation. The list is tentative. There are necessarily not complement pairs of crisis and adaption. Further text analysis of the focus groups transcripts will be necessary.

Category	Crisis	Adaption
Authorization and Obligations	<p>The plurality and complexity of authorization procedures hamper the development of aquaculture.</p> <p>In particular, the development of modern trout farms (using partly RAS¹⁰ technology) is hampered by nature protection regulations.</p> <p>Conservation focuses on the risks of aquaculture.</p> <p>The authorization of aquacultures takes place at county level. There, the officials are often non-experienced and uncertain regarding aquaculture practices.</p> <p>County authorities interpret regulations differently.</p> <p>Agricultural farms have privileges (e. g. building law); aquaculture does not.</p> <p>Drugs, which are approved for the terrestrial agriculture, are often not approved for aquaculture, too; although they are needed urgently.</p> <p>Hygiene regulations of retailers are too strict and complex as smallholders could manage as suppliers.</p>	<p>Central coordination of aquaculture authorizations.</p> <p>Upscaling of enterprises /farms to use economies of scale advantages. Here are still potentials for German trout producers. Large farms manage better the bureaucratic and legal obligations.</p> <p>Training of authorities' employees at county level.</p>
Climate Change	<p>Regions with low precipitation like carp areas in Bavaria will struggle with shortage of rainfalls.</p> <p>Water shortage will lead to stricter water license approvals and obligations.</p> <p>Increased temperatures will be a challenge for cold water species.</p> <p>Aquacultures will struggle with increased diseases and appearance of parasites caused by warmer summers.</p>	<p>Warm water fish like carp will have a better productivity.</p> <p>If the 2°C aim will be reached, the trout farms in Baden-Württemberg would manage the adaption towards changed environmental frameworks. Regarding salmonids, invest in partly RAS technology.</p> <p>RAS are well prepared for climate change.</p>

⁹ Rammstedt O. (2011): Krise In: Fuchs-Heinritz et al. (Hrsg.): Lexikon zur Soziologie. 5. Aufl. Wiesbaden: VS, p. 382.

¹⁰ Recirculating Aquaculture System; there is a range of different RAS definitions in the literature. We have a wide understanding of RAS and according to Pillay and Kutty RAS is defined as any applied aquaculture construction which treats the production water and re-use it for fish farming ((2005) Aquaculture: principles and practices. Blackwell, Oxford).

<p>Company Organisation</p>	<p>Traditional fish farming is not profitable as full-time business anymore.</p> <p>Traditional fish farming – in particular trout farming – is profitable as supplier of regional niche markets.</p> <p>Industrial fish production needs a lot of investments, more than family farms, which predominate the German sector, could effort.</p> <p>Marketing is a barrier of entrepreneurship: Either the fish farmer needs a large production to supply the wholesale or a developed direct marketing to sell small amounts of fish regionally. Both distribution strategies challenge newcomers.</p> <p>Imports dominate the German retail. Only a very small group of German producers are internationally competitive.</p>	<p>Diversification of small-scale farms towards new (service) fields close to fish farming (e.g. processing, gastronomy, touristic services)</p> <p>Upscaling of enterprises/farms to use economies of scale advantages and enhance profitability.</p> <p>Modernization of farms.</p>
<p>Consumer Behaviour</p>	<p>The expectations towards a sustainable aquaculture are too high and unrealistic.</p> <p>The plurality and variety of labels confuse the consumers. Partly wrong labelling destroys consumers' trust in domestic product quality.</p> <p>There are contradictions between consumers' expectations towards aquaculture products and consumers' behaviour: expectation of eco-friendly, sustainable fish farming versus decreasing demand for non-predatory fish which is cultured extensively (e.g. carp) versus low willingness to pay,</p> <p>You cannot change the consumers' behaviour via educational advertising.</p> <p>Although conservationists have strongly promoted the consumption of carp as most eco-friendly fish consumption, the demand of carp have not increased yet.</p>	<p>Highlighting the differences between species and production systems.</p> <p>Standardized and continuous communication towards consumer.</p> <p>Emphasize the product environment (e.g. tradition, regionalism).</p> <p>Enhance the traceability of products.</p> <p>Demand-orientated product development.</p>
<p>Differentiation</p>	<p>Aquaculture is a diverse sector with a variety of different species and different production systems. To generalize statements addressing one species/production system towards the whole sector is not valid.</p>	<p>Analysing problems and solutions separate per species and production systems.</p>
<p>Federalism</p>	<p>The disunity between the federal states and the national state as well as in between the federal states hampers the development of the German aquaculture sector.</p> <p>The missing national harmonization of regulation frameworks discourages investors.</p> <p>The European Maritime and Fisheries Fund (EMFF) is a well-aimed financial instrument of the Common Fisheries Policy. But, the EMFF application on federal state and therein county levels is divided into too small sections and responsibilities.</p>	<p>Standardization and simplification of regulation frameworks and authorization procedures.</p>

<p>Location Factors</p>	<p>Trout farms have to deal with old inherited water licenses, because they do not get new ones.</p> <p>There is a shortage of qualified staff.</p> <p>There is a shortage of space for aquaculture.</p> <p>Knowhow and new technologies are available, but their application is not diffused.</p> <p>High standards increase domestic production costs compared to international competitors.</p>	<p>Intensification of water usage.</p> <p>Defining space for aquaculture in space planning.</p> <p>Improving national scientific networking and networking between business and science.</p> <p>Duties for imported products with lower environmental, consumer or hygienic standards.</p>
<p>Image</p>	<p>Aquaculture has a negative image in society. Unreflected media reports tighten up the situation. The knowledge level of people regarding aquaculture topics is very low. People do not differ between single species and production systems.</p>	<p>Consequently, cultivation of image to reach prerogative of interpretation.</p> <p>Enhance cooperation between producers' associations.</p>
<p>Predators</p>	<p>In particular open systems like carp farms struggle with losses caused by predators like cormorant, European otter or damages through beaver activities; animals, which are strongly protected through nature protection laws.</p>	<p>Compensation payments.</p> <p>Subsidize defence actions.</p>

COMPETITIVENESS AND SUSTAINABLE SOURCING IN EUROPE FOR FISH AND SEAFOOD.

Focus Group Workshop and World Café, Rome, May 18-19 2016^{11,12}

Participants came from seafood industries, retail, sustainability initiatives, fisheries associations, FAO, DG Mare of the European Commission, as well as representatives of certification schemes and accreditation bodies on sustainable fishing and aquaculture.

Figure 1 Delegates concentrating on the cases presented

The workshop was divided into four sessions where participants identified challenges and shared their views on opportunities to motivate sustainable sourcing in practice. Presenters provided examples from their area of work and focused on:

“What are the bottlenecks and opportunities linked with sustainable sourcing in practice, future trends, certification schemes, and initiatives ensuring the sustainable dimensions of European seafood products.”

The World Café following the workshop further addressed the benefits and drawbacks of certification schemes for sustainability, measures to combat Illegal, unreported and Unregulated (IUU) fishing and discussed policy options, with the aim to identify gaps where more research and activities were needed.

In general, the view was that the criteria for sustainable sourcing was unclear. There are too many schemes and the different scope of certifications is confusing. The criteria for sustainability and responsibility are often not clear. Guidelines and recommendations are lacking for sustainability indicators and there is a need to establish “International” social and economic references for sustainability assessment. The problem is data collection and

Figure 2 Key “challenges” (Word Cloud frequency of terms used) discussed regarding sustainable sourcing and certification schemes

¹¹ The workshop summary and presentations are available on the project website, visit this link; <http://www.success-h2020.eu/success-workshops/workshop-rome-2016/>

¹² Guðrún Ólafsdóttir, Miriam Nourry, Simon Mardle, Marie-Luise Rau, José M.F. Polonco, Maria Cozzolino, Katrin Zander, Hildigunnur Sigurðardóttir, Bertrand LeGallic, Sigurður Bogason (2016). Competitiveness and Sustainable Sourcing in Europe for Fish and Seafood, Working Document WP9 SUCCESS H2020 project GA 635188. Focus Group Workshop and World Café, Rome, May 18-19, 2016.

multiple audits which impose cost and a burden for producers. The following issues were highlighted by the stakeholders:

- Simplify the certification processes and make standards or guidelines (checklists) accessible to motivate harmonisation
 - ⇒ One certification instead of multiple
 - ⇒ Develop a cost-effective tool / framework for standards / make checklists available on-line
 - ⇒ Benchmarking of labels → role for Global Sustainable Seafood Initiative (GSSI) needs further recognition
 - ⇒ Need exists for evaluating the rules in place, as policy is creating new rules; rarely deleting or simplifying rules → deregulation or delegation of power should be further considered.
 - Decentralization / Regionalization / devolution of power
 - ⇒ Improving monitoring of fish stock status to ensure their sustainability
 - ⇒ Measures to avoid unfair competition and creating equal “playing field” between food commodities,
 - Including regard to social standards,
 - Ensure transparency and information sharing,
 - Avoid creation of market bottlenecks and use policy as steward for sustainable sourcing, e.g. through criteria for public tenders (including schools, hospitals and public canteens),
 - Business should focus on transparency along the entire chain and understand consumer preferences.
- **Aquaculture:** Existing standards are covering best practices and responsibility not sustainability.
- **Fisheries:** Imperative to maintain stocks and livelihoods for the future.
- **Role of research:** Requirements to achieving sustainability and research should play a role:
 - ⇒ Common traceability protocols needed,
 - ⇒ Sharing responsibility and costs of achieving (and certifying for) sustainability,
 - ⇒ Finding an overarching solution aiming for equitable profits for all in the value chain,

Way forward for research in sustainable seafood:

- ⇒ Applied research and knowledge sharing
- ⇒ Ecosystem scenario analysis
- ⇒ Responsive science for future fisheries science partnerships
- ⇒ Consumer preferences (innovation, new markets)
- ⇒ Where will we be in 2030? Assumed sustainability with no need for ecolabels?
- ⇒ How to minimise costs in the value chain?
- ⇒ Ensure competitiveness with other proteins

Figure 3 - Participants Group and (right) World Café session in Practice

PRICE TRANSMISSION AND MARKET POWER IN THE SEAFOOD VALUE CHAIN IN EUROPE:

Stakeholders' perception analysis, World Café, Santander, May 10-12, 2017¹³

The University of Cantabria, organized a workshop and a World Café event on "Price transmission and market power in the seafood value chain in Europe", in collaboration with the MarkMar and the project coordinator (UBO), to present the results of the analyses conducted in the context of "Analysis of price transmission and market power".

The objective was to identify current trends, challenges and opportunities to enhance competitiveness in the seafood value chain in Europe. The main themes considered were trade flows and market power and the implications on price interactions along the seafood value chains.

The workshop gathered 32 agents and stakeholders from 12 countries (Spain, France, UK, Finland, Greece, Italy, Poland, Iceland, Netherlands, Portugal, USA, and Australia) involved in the seafood value chain

A World Café session was also organized in which all the participants actively participated in the discussion of several themes related with the seafood value chains in the EU. The aim was that each participant provided its expertise (related with a species, a market, a step in the chain, policies, trade, etc.) to the discussion. The themes discussed were determined based on topics that were considered relevant for the ongoing work in WP4. The common topics which emerged from the discussions at each table were grouped according to the following main themes.

- *What is the influence of international trade on domestic prices formation?*
- *Market delimitation - Market power - Price transmission: Forward and backward vertical integration in the seafood value chain / Market power and bargain power*
- *Challenging costs in seafood value chains in Europe: Costs of trading seafood*

Table 1 Word clouds showing frequency of terms used in World Café discussions

International trade influence on domestic price formation?

Integration in seafood value chain – market power?

Changing view of market channels?

Costs of trading seafood?

¹³ Further information on the workshop is available on the SUCCESS project website, visit this link: <http://www.success-h2020.eu/success-workshops/workshop-cantabria-2017/>

Additional issues identified¹⁴ reflected the stakeholders’ concerns regarding the changing views of markets, labelling and certification, knowledge sharing, training and communication and barriers of regulations in trade.

- *Changing view of markets and market channels*
- *Knowledge sharing, training and communication*
- *Labelling and certification in the seafood value chain*
- *Barriers and regulations in trade*

Table 2 – Word clouds showing frequency of terms arising from World Café discussions

The Knowledge sharing, training and communication?

Labelling and certification in the seafood value chain?

Barriers and regulations in trade

Stakeholder comment:
 Inside EU we hear that the EU industry is complaining about how many rules and normative they need to follow, but this is also the case for their competitors outside the EU.

- The EU also makes requirements on non-EU companies when trading to the EU and then,
- the EU does not ask for this to EU producers,
- or possibly the EU asks for some rules to accept imports into the EU area, but then the EU products, when are exported to other places do not follow these rules.

The stakeholders mentioned as well other core traits of the market, like:

- Price transmission differs between farmed and wild caught seafood products
- Constant supply throughout the year and price stability is required for increasing market base
- Quality isn’t the only purchase decision criterion, consumer perceptions do matter,
- The market structure differs, and prices differ accordingly, and markets can change
- Tradition in consumption is a driver and results in specific demands
- Social media creates new value for some species, product image is important, and storytelling can be a useful tool

¹⁴ Olafsdottir, G., Le Gallic, B., Cozzolini, M., Gambino, M. Mardle, S., Lorrente, I. Bogason, S.G. (2017). Stakeholders' perception on PRICE TRANSMISSION AND MARKET POWER IN THE SEAFOOD VALUE CHAIN IN EUROPE. SUCCESS World Café, Santander, WP9 Working Document SUCCESS H2020 project GA 635188

SUCCESS Workshop in price integration in the seafood value chain in the EU – Santander, May 10-12

SUCCESS, a Research and Innovation Project (2015 – 2018)

SUCCESS is an H2020 project financed by the EC with focus on the Strategic Use of Competitiveness towards Consolidating the Economic Sustainability of the European Seafood Sector (<http://www.success-h2020.eu/>).

The **University of Cantabria**, as part of this project and leader of the WP4, has organized a workshop to present the results of the analysis conducted in the context of the **Task 4.2 Analysis of price transmission and market power**.

The workshop, held in the city of **Santander** in May, 10th-12th, has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 635188.

Agents from 12 countries

The workshop, introduced by the project coordinator Bertrand Le Gallic from UBO, has gathered 32 agents and stakeholders from 12 countries (Spain, France, UK, Finland, Greece, Italy, Poland, Iceland, Netherlands, Portugal, USA, and Australia) involved in the seafood value chain to present and discuss the results, generating a better understanding with the knowledge, expertise and experience of the industry and policy makers.

The methodology of World Café has been used to enhance group dialogue. Directed by Markmar, three rotating tables - 1) EU trade flows and domestic markets of seafood commodities, 2) market delimitation – market power, and 3) challenging costs - were set to discuss value chains in Europe.

The workshop has served to provide inputs to other SUCCESS CSs and WPs, as well as complete and improve the results and conclusions that will be presented later in the report.

- Session 1. Presentation with Aurora de Blas. Ministry of Agriculture and Fisheries, Food and the Environment.
- Session 2. Price integration analysis in the seafood value chain, an overview
- Session 3. Price integration in the Salmonids value chain
- Session 4. Price integration in the coastal fisheries
- Session 5. Price integration in the Seabream and Seabass value chain
- Session 6. Price integration in the whitefish value chain
- Session 7. Price integration in the carp value chain
- Session 8. Price integration analysis in flatfish value chain
- Session 9. World Café. Seafood value chains

- Session 10. Price integration analysis in mussel value chain
- Session 11. Shellfish value chain in USA
- Session 12. Final discussion and conclusions

Participants: Bertrand Le Gallic, Laurent Le Grel, Simon Mardle, Jarno Virtanen, Avdelas Lamprakis, Maria Cozzolino, Monica Gambino, Adam Mytlewski, Malgorzata Kieliszewska, Sigurdur Bogason, Gudrún, Ólafsdóttir, Ignacio Llorente, Ladislao Luna, José Manuel Fernández, José Luis Fernández, María Odrizola, Elisa Baraibar, Mike Turenhout, José Antonio González, Milos Dukat, Rocío Robles, Inocencio Rodríguez, Javier Martínez, Roberto Romero, Carl-Christian Schmidt, Bill Taylor, Francisco Fonseca, Roy Palmer, Weiwei Wang, Aurora de Blas.

SUCCESS CO-CREATION PLATFORM AND CASE STUDY ON COASTAL FISHERIES

Slow Fish International, Genova, 18-21 May 2017

The SUCCESS team organised a pavilion at the Slow Fish event in Genova and conducted two round table sessions focusing on specific case studies. These were linked to projection of documentary movies prepared on coastal fisheries by the SUCCESS project. Also one synthetic session was hosted by gathering all the invited stakeholders, LIFE representatives, SUCCESS team and visitors. Discussions

Figure 4 - The SUCCESS Pavilion in Genova

about the difficulties raised by the management of shared resources between small scale and large scale fleets, and the complexity of the EU policies and the risk of contradictions or misunderstandings in interpretation of these policies at national, regional or local levels were debated by those attending.

The team presented 12 posters and five documentary movies were presented by invited stakeholders involved in the movies that were screened at selected times during the whole event. The SUCCESS team consisted of 10 participants from partners NISEA, UBO, IFREMER UNIPA, Fishpass and MarkMar. During the four days more than 200 visitors came to the stand (pavilion) to be informed about the project.

The SUCCESS stand was honored by the visit of Renata Briano from the EU parliament, the president of the Slowfish scientific committee (Silvestro Greco), a delegation of the Sicilian regional administration (the general director of the fishery department Dario Cartabellotta), the Italian senator Andrea Cioffiand and many fisheries institutional and stakeholders including our guests and LIFE representatives (Jerry Percy and Claudia Orlandini).

Two journalists ensured a strong media coverage of our events (Eurofish magazine and Pesceinrete, an Italian magazine, see news clippings in Appendix II of this report).

Survey questionnaire (Slow Fish)

A questionnaire was developed to use for interviews at the Slow fish event. Google forms was used to create an on-line version of the questionnaire and a link was made available to the participants to collect the responses¹⁵. More than 50 feed-back questionnaires were filled in by visitors, including foreign guests, and the results analysed by partner MarkMar.

Do you consider that European Coastal Fisheries are sustainable? 48 responses

¹⁵ Reference: Ólafsdóttir, G., Daures, F., Malvarosa, L., Sabatella R. F., Paolucci C., Nourry M., Pirrone C., Fazio G., Fricano, S., Le Grel, L., Bogason, S. G. 2017. Working Document WP9 Stakeholders' perception analysis, Questionnaire and Round table. SUCCESS Co-creation platform and Case Study on Coastal Fisheries. SlowFish International event, Genova, Italy May, 2017.

The objective of the survey was to assess the stakeholders' perception towards key themes that had been identified to influence the long term economic viability and competitiveness of European fisheries and aquaculture sectors e.g.: "Regulations", "Markets", "Seafood Value Chains" and "Sustainability".

SUSTAINABILITY includes several issues regarding competitiveness and was selected by one third of the respondent who recognised the importance of ensuring sustainable resource utilization for the future. An opportunity was identified to promote fisheries as environmentally sustainable and able to create employment. This was supported by the view that there was a growing tendency to look at environmental initiatives which ensure the sustainability of fish as a resource. Furthermore, promoting transparency on the regional products could enhance local fishermen from a market perspective. Fishermen need to stay in employment and local markets must be willing to buy from the small fisheries and not only focus on making big contracts. Also, sustainability would entail to promote an equilibrium between the production systems and the resource and it would also be essential to consider the value chain because of the importance of the logistics involved.

In terms of the issues related to the MARKET, the area of origin, how the product was processed, traceability and certification were considered important information. In this context, it was mentioned that "the rationale for harvesting is to get the goods to consumers in environmental friendly manner and at fair price" and "only proper marketing strategies can ensure sustainability". The view was expressed that: *"Certification schemes and labelling would help consumers make the right choice"*.

Issues influencing competitiveness of fisheries and aquaculture products in Europe (frequency=64)

REGULATIONS were considered important for the competitiveness of the sectors and sustainability is ensured by effective regulation which need to be adapted to local conditions. The regulation on area of origin and traceability are two fundamental parameters that influence the competitiveness of fishery products. Traceability guarantees the origin and protects consumers. Europe has many laws that must protect these sectors, including the fishermen, although it was stated by one of the respondents from local fisheries that *"Regulation is very invasive, but somewhat limited in supporting fishermen"*.

Regulations can also be a barrier for example the limited maximum number of vessels that make a certain kind of fishing can limit the production and other regulations can potentially affect the production and marketing.

Issues related to SEAFOOD VALUE CHAINS that were commented on by the respondents included the importance of the economics, and adding value is the most important but also sustainability as well as involvement of the key stakeholder for example the fishermen.

For small scale fishery increase of the added value is pivotal to achieve economic and environmental sustainability. Furthermore, the importance of cooperation among different sectors was mentioned. It is necessary that in the coastal fishery, in particular the small one, it would be possible to activate processes that enforce the local governance and processes of collaboration between fishing firms and local actors.

When respondents were asked to mention what came to mind when considering competitiveness of the fisheries and aquaculture sector, different aspects were mentioned. The importance of fisheries and preservation of family firms for local communities was acknowledged as well as the importance of increasing the quality and considering biodiversity.

MUSSEL FARMING IN ITALY - OPPORTUNITIES FOR GROWTH AND VALORISATION

Workshop Cattolica, ITALY, 27 MAY 2017

The main objective of the workshop was to meet the stakeholders and disseminate the results already produced in the Mussel Case Study of the SUCCESS project. Also, to receive information from the workshop participants through discussions about macro-themes defined in the workshop agenda. The workshop started with a presentation of the SUCCESS project and focused on the “mussel” case study, giving context elements on the European and Italian sector and the value chain associated.

During the two roundtables, stakeholders exchanged on environmental impacts and outlook perspective for the sector. The workshop was useful to share best practices among producers but also common issues that, in different Italian regions, are resolved differently, creating strong and significant imbalances and which may involve economic damage to mussel companies. The workshop succeeded in encouraging the various stakeholders to participate dynamically in the discussion.

The workshop has helped to gain a better understanding and testimony from the producers of Cozza di SCARDOVARI DOP, the consortium of the Italian Protected Designation of Origin (PDO)

Main results:

- High interest in the issues addressed
- High added issues compared to those initially proposed as a basis for discussion
- Validation of value chain data for mussels in Italy
- Great interest in knowing future results of the SUCCESS project’s Mussel case study.

*Eurofish magazine 4/2017**

Giuseppe Prioli, President of the European Molluscs Producers Association (EMPA), presented an overview of the European and Italian mussel sector and its main opportunities. In 2014, 450,880 tonnes of mussels were farmed in the EU. Spain is the biggest producer, with 195,375 tonnes, compared to Italy, which produces 63,731 tonnes.

Italian mussel sector faces many obstacles to increase production: Eraldo Rambaldi, Director of the Association of Mediterranean Aquaculture Producers (AMA) elaborated on the main issues currently concerning the mussel sector.

The lack of spatial planning in Italy is one of the main obstacles prohibiting increased production, since mussel farming competes against many other sectors for the space it needs. Another issue is that the local authorities administer the national regulation in different ways that hinder producers, who are working now to get these problems solved. The Italian sector consists of many small, family-based farmers, who are often former fishermen, so the lack of professionalism and small size are also issues that need to be addressed. Merging into larger units or cooperating to form a consortium of producers under one professional seller are some solutions that would help the sector get more bargaining power over supermarkets.

A case study from the SUCCESS project was presented by Sophie Girard of France’s IFREMER – AMURE Brest. Countries chosen for the study included Spain, Italy, France and the Netherlands as the top four producers in Europe. According to the study, in 2014, about 1,000 people were employed in the Italian mussel sector in 159 companies. The mussel prices indicator for the Netherlands was €1,4 per kilogram compared with €0,73 per kilogram in Italy, and overall, the blue mussels in northern Europe had higher valorisation when compared with the Mediterranean mussels. The costs structure was also presented; one remarkable result was the labour costs distribution among Spain (62%), Italy (39%), France (33%) and the Netherlands (24%), revealing that the industry is more concentrated in a few companies in the north. Future market perspectives foresee increased demand for organic products and new value-added products; however, it was also discussed at the workshop how organically produced mussels do not always fetch higher prices, making the value of investments in organic certification uncertain. The study mentioned additional bottleneck factors that would restrict the growth of the sector, including the environment (whether natural variations, or other influences causing mussel mortalities or other economic losses resulting from periods of sales closures), the difficulty of obtaining licenses for new sites, the lack of professionalism and organization in the sector’s structure, and the ability of some sectors to increase the valorisation of their products through marketing.

The workshop for stakeholders in the Italian mussel farming industry brought together 40 participants representing 30% of the sector.

Small companies, big potential: Maria Cozzolino from NISEA, an economic research institute specialising in fisheries and aquaculture, also presented an overview of the Italian mussel value chain. One of the main issues discussed at the workshop was the relatively small size of the Italian mussel companies that resulted in limited negotiation power when dealing with supermarkets. The presentation recommended that the Italian sector consider more vertical organization, so it could sell directly to the supermarkets with a much higher valorisation and productivity. Currently, in the French market, 82% of the organic mussels are sold in supermarkets, while in Italy, 65% of mussels is sold in supermarkets from wholesalers.

Ideas for improvement going forward: During the afternoon, the stakeholders were very active in presenting their company's activities and views at the three roundtable discussions. In the workshop, the participants discussed bureaucratic procedures, certification, management, vertical integration and distribution, and room for future improvements.

One main issue discussed was the demand for market access. One producer of oysters had waited three years for the license to produce. By reducing the bureaucratic control, the licensing process could be made speedier. e banks also limited sh farmers, making it hard for them to get loans. The participants would like to have the same conditions for approving loans as the Italian agriculture sector. Moreover, they would like to see farmer compensations between regions to be made fairer. Currently, those who lose their production due to weather conditions are subjected to compensations regulated by regional authorities that may vary from 0 to 90%. As the workshop concluded, stakeholders walked away with new market information and the opportunity to have expressed and discussed their views in a good atmosphere.

The meeting at Cattolica represented, for the Italian mussel sector, the first official meeting after they formed an association that would represent their needs and protect their interests. The atmosphere was extremely open to research as well as the exchange of professional experiences. Immediate impacts of the meeting have been a greater cohesion among the mussel producers and a higher interest in improving production performance. As a result, interest rates have risen both in the comparison of production costs and in the different value chains in the major mussel producer countries, such as Italy, France, Spain, and even Greece, an emerging producer among the four.

* Eurofish magazine; https://issuu.com/eurofish/docs/eurofish_magazine_4_2017

WORKSHOP ON BLUE GROWTH: SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF THE FISHERY & AQUACULTURE SECTOR

Santander, Spain 7-8 September 2017

WORKSHOP ON BLUE GROWTH: SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF THE FISHERY & AQUACULTURE SECTOR (SUCCESS H2020)

Santander, 7 - 8 September 2017.

BLUE GROWTH

“Blue Growth is the long term strategy to support sustainable growth in the marine and maritime sectors as a whole. Seas and oceans are drivers for the European economy and have great potential for innovation and growth. It is the maritime contribution to achieving the goals of the Europe 2020 strategy for smart, sustainable and inclusive growth..” — (European Commission)

Brochure and materials delivered to attendees.

WORKING GROUP

Representatives of institutions highly involved in Blue Growth, such as Ministerio de Agricultura y Pesca, Alimentación y Medio Ambiente (MAPAMA), Oceanic Platform of the Canary Islands (PLOCAN), Coastal Ocean Observing and Forecasting System (SOCIB), IDES-UC, National Association of Sea and Fish Canned Food Producers (ANFACO-CECOPESCA), Xunta de Galicia, MSC, Grupo Consorcio, Thünen Institut, EU- DG MARE, AND International, Cantabria Confederation of Cofradías and Office of Food Quality of Cantabria (ODECA) attended the event. The conferences, discussion panels, and the continuous dialogue between the attendants have given rise to remarkable conclusions that will be highlighted through this brief communication.

✓ Policies for Blue Growth strategy

- The Blue Growth strategy can boost the growth of the European fishery and aquaculture sector and ensure its sustainability. This requires incorporating and improving information on the marine environment and enhancing marine research and knowledge.
- The Blue Growth strategy entails a major policy integration effort, so far dispersed, which will lead to a better understanding of the impact that these policies can have on a geographical area, as well as to produce positive synergies between different agents and improve the capacity to generate ideas.

Jose Luis González Serrano. General Director of Fisheries Management (MAPAMA)

✓ Knowledge spaces in the Blue Growth

- To contribute to the Blue Growth it is necessary to use tools for the economic development of the fishing and aquaculture sector in Europe. Some of these tools are: innovation and technological development through multisector projects, strategic innovation and technological development plans, fisheries diversification, production and marketing plans of producer organizations, strategic aquaculture plans, green economy, and the operational program of the Spanish Federation of Municipalities and Provinces (FEMP).

It is important to keep in mind that sustainable strategies must be equipped with management and monitoring mechanisms, which are simple, agile, and effective.

• **Q: Are there projects based on Blue Growth in progress?**

Discussion panel. Generation of knowledge spaces. Carlos Botana, Octavio Llínas, Joaquín Tintoré, Igor de la Casa.

The tool that can best be adapted to these aims are through knowledge spaces around Blue Growth as it is developing the Vigo Port Authority. These spaces are materialized through centers of excellence of the Blue Growth. Carlos Botana Lagarón, representing the Port of Vigo, explained the work developed in this regard by the institution, which is seeking to be a reference model of Blue Growth at European level, promoting competitiveness, efficiency and sustainability in all its activities, facilities and services in the 2020 horizon. The Port of Vigo benefits from an ecosystem of knowledge formed by academic institutions, research institutions and technology centers. An example of the creation of knowledge spaces within the Blue Growth initiative of the Port of Vigo is the launching of the project "Blue careers" which aims to update and promote the qualification of professionals in the port sector and their adaptability to the market in order to maintain employability and to improve their professional progression.

✓ **New technologies applied to the fishing activities funding**

An important factor for the Blue strategy and the promotion of the sustainability of the European fisheries and aquaculture sector is to facilitate a better access to financing. Providing adequate information to intermediaries and financial analysts would make it possible to create a benchmarking index for fishery and aquaculture products.

"A price index of fishery and aquaculture products would enable financial agents to hedge risks in the sector by creating a market for derivatives and/or future contracts; and to create a ship valuation system, which would allow and objective quantification of ship severance indemnities or an economic assessment of fishing opportunities and TACs". – Ladislao Luna (IDES-UC)

Ladislao Luna (IDES UC).

✓ **The impact of certifications and quality labels**

Organizations can request several ecolabels and quality certifications. Ecolabels are a way to guarantee the sustainability of fishery resources.

Conference about eco-labeling of fishery and aquaculture products. Carola González – EU DG MARE

✓ **Why are fishery products certified?**

- To improve the image of the company.
- In response to market pressures (distributors and/or consumers)

✓ **Which are the barriers that companies find to certify their products?**

- According to the companies of the sector, the biggest problem is related to administrative procedures and paperwork, as well as the costs derived from the certification. Smaller companies include the lack of information. However, certification costs may be acceptable to small producers when they are grouped or associated, for example, in the case of Asturian octopus producers to obtain the label MSC.

José Luis Fernández – IDES UC- during Q&A

Packaging examples of products with ecolabels.

✓ **Which is the consumer's perception of quality certifications and ecolabels?**

- European consumers, especially Germans and Italians, are willing to pay a premium price for fishery and aquaculture products with certain attributes related to sustainability of resources.
- In Europe, there is a strong growth in the demand for organic aquaculture products in the period 2012-2016, with an increase of 73%. This growth is led by the UK with sales last year of more than 20,000 tons and an annual growth of 43%. It is followed by countries such as Germany (sales of 14,000 tons and 8% annual growth) and France (sales of almost 5,000 tons and 18% annual growth).
- European consumers of fishery and aquaculture products show greater preference for domestic or local products compared to products from other countries. In Germany, consumers are willing to pay more for local organic aquaculture products, or products from companies that care about animal welfare

✓ **How do product certifications affect sales and margins?**

- There is a slightly positive perception of companies regarding product certifications. This perception is higher when dealing with increasing revenues or sales than when dealing with margins. Larger companies have a more positive perception than small companies.

✓ **Perspectives for organic aquaculture**

The conclusions drawn from the expert discussion during the workshop on this topic are highlighted below.

- Organic aquaculture has gained importance in certain species (salmon, seabream, seabass and trout) and countries (Ireland and Denmark), while in others there is a potential market (organic mussel farming).
- A strong increase in European production and demand is expected in the coming years.
- Producers' dissatisfaction with the economic performance of organic aquaculture is latent, since it cannot be taken for granted (false expectations).
- There is some reluctance of retailers over organic products as it is not well differentiated from other products.
- There is confusion among consumers with different product certifications (ecological, organic, sustainable, bio...)

✓ **Restrictions that limit the development of the market of organic production**

- The higher price paid for these products is an important factor that makes this market still a niche market.
- Limited supply or availability of these products.
- Competition among products with ecolabel or sustainable certification and organic products.

Conference: Organic aquaculture in Europe. Implementation, economic impact and acceptance of the value chain. Dominique Aviat (AND International).

Conference: European consumer perception of fishery and aquaculture products on ecolabelling. Katrin Zander (Thünen Institut).

Discussion panel. Sustainability of fishery and aquaculture products: problems, policies and the impact on the sector. Laura Rodríguez (MSC), Antonio Rodríguez (Xunta Galicia), Rosana Varela (ANFACO CECOPESEA), Eduardo Sanfilippo (Grupo Consorcio), Jose Luis Fernández (IDES UC).

✓ **Recommendations to promote the development of organic aquaculture**

- Promote a significant increase in the level of production of organic farms in order to obtain economies of scale and reduce production and distribution costs.
- Focus production on a few species (salmon, trout and seabass/seabream).
- Strengthen the identity, credibility and readability of organic labels to differentiate themselves from ecolabels.
- Ensure that producers of organic aquaculture, as well as regulatory authorities in each country, have optimal access to regulatory information and European funds to prevent a lack of knowledge from hindering the potential growth of this type of production.
- Inform organic farmers of the actual costs of organic production, especially the costs of certification, which are perceived by the sector as very high when they are not.

✓ **Social responsibility of the Spanish canning sector.**

Spain is the EU's main producer of canned seafood and the second largest in the world after Thailand. It is a consolidated sector, with a sustained growth. It has a significant weight in the social and socio-economic dimension of large areas of the Spanish coast. The seafood canning industry stands out for its tradition, experience and know-how. This sector provides a modern technology that bets on R&D&I, and follows a strategy of differentiation and specialization as a development strategy. However, the maturity of the market acts as a barrier in the implementation of these innovation in the sector.

The sector is strongly committed to sustainability, quality and food safety, as well as other principles of corporate governance. The long-term conservation of fishery resources is key to the future of the sector, thus it is firmly committed to sustainability in order to ensure the supply of resources in a responsible and sustainable way by complying with rules, laws, or regulations and improving scientific knowledge. The sector is also committed to Human Rights and labor rights, strictly respecting the regulatory framework.

Discussion panel. Strategies for the sustainable development of the fishing sector in Cantabria. Fernando Mier Lobato (ODECA), Miguel Fernández (Presidente de la federación de Cofradías de Pescadores de Cantabria), y Ladislao Luna (IDES UC).

Conference: Social responsibility in the value chain of fishery and aquaculture products: initiatives, challenges and socioeconomic impact. Rosana Varela (ANFACO-CECOPESCA).

Some of the measures to be adopted by associations of processors to promote technological innovation have been the following: optimization of the exploitation of fish for a better use, development of new products, identification of new products / species with commercial interest, extraction of high added-value compounds for use in the pharmaceutical industry, cosmetics and food industry, design of new packaging and improved food shelf life.

In addition, new markets have also been accessed through the development of new products made with emerging species (corvine, halibut, perch, etc.) and new heat treatment systems applicable to the food industry, based on induction technology, have been developed to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and energy consumption.

✓ **Proposal regarding environmental and socioeconomic sustainability in the European fishery and canning industry.**

- An observatory for traceability from different associations in the sector, with the aim of promoting the defense of fair competition in the EU market, allowing to promote monitoring and compliance of illegal fishing regulation (IUU).
- Competing on a level playing field on the EU market for canned tuna.
- International cooperation programs to improve the training of national authorities and local communities with a gender approach and a resources sustainability approach.

✓ **Recommendations for implementing CSR in the value chain**

✓ **ENVIRONMENTAL issues**

- Development of a code of conduct or supplier code, establishing minimum standards that must be fulfilled by the suppliers.
- Choose suppliers with CSR-related certifications.
- Comply with existing codes of conduct.
- Measures to be taken in product processing: reduce water consumption, reduce fish consumption, optimize waste generation, reduce energy consumption, and improve design of packaging.
- Encourage citizen cooperation with the environment (recycling)

✓ **SOCIOECONOMIC issues**

- Promote healthy behavior in the consumer
- Take part in sectorial promotional campaigns that reach the final consumer
- Use labelling to raise awareness about responsible consumption
- Provide the consumer with information about the product and the food (about sustainability or production techniques)
- Disclose a sustainability report

MAIN CONCLUSIONS ON BLUE GROWTH

- The Blue Growth strategy can boost the growth of the European fisheries and aquaculture sector and ensure its sustainability.
- Most effective tools for improving competitiveness, efficiency and sustainability of activities in fisheries and aquaculture sector are technological innovation, differentiation strategies based on development of new products and processes and the generation of shared knowledge spaces for stakeholders and the sector.
- Information systems can become a driver of Blue Growth strategy in the fisheries and sustainability sector. These information systems can be used to create a benchmark price index for risk management and/or control of costs of production.
- Ecolabels and quality certifications give a good image to the product, but they entail costs that are not compensated with their impact on sales. However, this situation may improve due to the increasing demand of responsible products in Europe.
- Spanish seafood canning sector is a modern sector that focuses on the conservation of fishery resources and technology. However, maturity of this industry is a barrier to the implementation of innovations in this sector.

Aula Bringas. Palacio de la Magdalena.

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FUTURE TRADE IN SEAFOOD - SUCCESS CO-CREATION PLATFORM

Brussels, 10-11 October 2017

FUTURE TRADE OF SEAFOOD: WORKSHOP ON NON-TARIFF MEASURES IN THE FISHERIES & AQUACULTURE VALUE CHAINS (SUCCESS H2020)

Brussels, 10-11 October 2017.

NON-TARIFF MEASURES (NTM)

NTMs are regulations that determine the conditions under which international trade takes place and are found in virtually every country. NTMs are often put in place for non-economic reasons, e.g. standards to protect the environment, animal and plant health as well as food safety. They also include economic measures, such as import quotas and financial measures, and technical measures such as proof of origin. Although legitimate and used as public policy measures, NTMs can constitute trade barriers that restrict imports to home countries and restrict exports to other countries. This can result in "playing fields" that are not level and is relevant to both intra and extra EU trade

Setting the scene

The SUCCESS project hosted a workshop with key stakeholders to provide first hand-information for Non-Tariff Measures (NTMs) in EU fisheries and aquaculture sector value chains. Both sectors rely on imports and exports. Recent global events, transparency in trade arrangements and technological developments are potentially changing the trade environment and which NTMs affect trade. **The specific aim of the workshop was to identify which NTMs matter and need to be addressed for the EU fishery/aquaculture sector.** An approach of identifying the actual issues at hand was taken with professionals in the trade of seafood to inform and improve EU policy.

NTMs have been defined according to the MAST (Multi-Agency Support Team) classification into Technical measures and Non-technical measures for imports and measures for exports. The technical measures include *Sanitary and Phytosanitary Measures* (SPS), which are affecting food safety and consumers, and *Technical Barriers to trade* (TBT) dealing with compatibility to labelling, standards on technical specifications and quality requirements, and other measures protecting the environment. Other measures relate to pre-shipment inspections and customs formalities which are classified separately.

UNCTAD, CLASSIFICATION OF NON-TARIFF MEASURES - (2012)
http://unctad.org/en/PublicationsLibrary/ditctab20122_en.pdf

Twenty-one participants attended the workshop, of which eleven were invited stakeholders from across Europe who presented examples of NTMs affecting the industries and their views on improvements needed in terms of policy options.

Four dimensions of NTMs

1. MEASURE: according to MAST classification
2. PRODUCT: specific product (incl code) and product group that is affected by a measure.
3. COUNTRY: Country that imposes the specific MEASURE on the PRODUCT; and Country that is affected by the specific MEASURE, where countries affected are identified based on WTO rules.
4. TIME: date that the MEASURE is enforced.

Impacts of BREXIT, free trade agreements, and booming shifts in international trade policies affected through Non-Tariff-Measures (NTMs) were among the topics discussed

SPS measure identified as barrier - Export from UK to Japan

HEALTH AND SAFETY ISSUE – USE OF ADDITIVES

Nephrops are dipped in 4HR (hexyl resorcinol) in the UK to avoid black spots in the shrimp. Import from UK producers were not approved into Japan since 4HR is not on their list of additives. There is a procedure to get an additive approved but in fact it is costly and takes 3-5 years. The Japanese market for seafood is huge and thus very lucrative but imports have been stalled due to this issue

It was noted that „In business you have to be in line with rules of the market“. However, transparency of the scientific reasons behind why certain additives are banned, are lacking and it would be of interest to know what other countries (including Japan) are using as alternatives to banned additives?

Better international trade policies for support to speed up processes in negotiations and to save cost would be a proposed solution and provide for healthy competition as much of cost falls to the trader.

In this case it would be useful to apply the NTM categorisation and identify the regulation behind it. Japan is part of the NTM categorisation, which is used in negotiations between governments and could influence trade agreements. There needs to be a structure and transparency, but NTMs are perceived as complex and therefore guidelines for exporters from EU should be available where potential cost and bottlenecks to enter markets should be identified.

SPS measure identified as barrier - Import to EU from India

IMPORTS FROM INDIA - SHRIMP AND AQUACULTURE “A message from Indian producers”

Control of 50% of imported aquaculture shrimps and fish from India is done at every veterinary border control point in the EU, doubling up on testing already done in India due to trust issues. The reason for testing is the concern of antibiotic residues in shrimps from India.

The integrated computerized TRACE system is being used at check points that provide overview of all results. There is a question of, why is there this doubling up? It becomes an issue of Europe’s competitiveness in the supply of seafood. Additional testing does not result in improved quality, as long as the first tests can be trusted. It is reported that the test results at check points reflect the tests already made in India. The delays caused by the testing has

huge additional costs which are all covered by the importer.

Europe is competing with other lucrative markets such as China. Such competition with other markets might make importers/exporters look to other markets rather than Europe due to the strict governance and extra costs involved to keep products fresh at every check points.

TBT measures – Origin and traceability verification

Future trade of Seafood - Importance of Export

Origin is an important issue. Re-labelling and fraud of species are common. Food security is therefore compromised. Full transparency is essential to ensure trust and trustworthy information flow along the value chain.

“This industry is not as mature as we think it is. We need to find a solution.”

There is a need for the implementation of policy and technological frameworks where information cannot be misused or manipulated. Educating the consumer is needed, as ignorance is being exploited in the value chain. No technology can replace human handling but it is something to be solved in any new system proposed. USA are working on a new solution that Europe will have to keep up with. Solutions in trade such as “block chain” that are being used in other industries are at the forefront of some of the changes being implemented around the world.

Traceability – new blockchain technologies

TRACEABILITY AND LABELLING

Supply chain becomes supply network

Supply chain transparency by use of Blockchain technology runs 24/7 all year round guaranteeing efficiency.

- *Everything can move faster and more smoothly.*
- *Affordable to have full chain traceability system.*
- *USA will implement.*
- *EU have to be ahead of the game, first or second.*
- *Standards and regulations need to be in place.*

Transmission and collection of data is fully ensured by the technology. Smartphone devices can be developed to facilitate the service. The technology is developing, it will come. It is being pursued in other industries. It can be viewed as a disruptive technology, easy to use, and available for everyone. Processor inserts data and makes it accessible to those, who need the information. No more paperwork.

But there are pending questions. How do we motivate users? Who pays? Who bears the upfront costs for proving the technology? No more bending rules or responsibility.

TBT measures – IUU and certification

FAO MEMBER COUNTRIES

Two examples of NTMs were identified that impact seafood trade and how companies/traders are affected:

1. *IUU (illegal, unreported and unregulated) is the an important NTM for some countries. “Red tape” countries cannot import to the EU. For the exporter, this means loss of market and for the EU importer it is loss of raw material. Developing countries are providers for 50% of global exports when looking at source for the EU Market.*
2. *Auditing and eco-labelling is a big issue due to the costs involved.*

Global movement to stop IUU:

1. **Combatting IUU fishing requires a strong political will and concerted action, including at regional levels through RFMOs, by Flag States, Port States, Coastal States and Market States.**
Signing the PSMA (Port state measure agreement) and aligning national CDS (catch documentation scheme) with FAO CDS guidelines provides a global record for vessels and CDS to work hand in hand to reduce IUU.
2. **Develop national / regional certification schemes benchmark – GSSI (Global Sustainable Seafood Initiative)**

TBT measures – IUU and reefer vessels

Influence of IUU Fishing regulations for Logistic of Seafood and International trade

Delays in clearance of shipments between Iceland, Norway, Faroe Islands and EU countries - mainly Baltic States. This is because of the 3 days' notice required to deliver information and catch certificates according to EC 1005/2008

CHAPTER 2, ART. 6: "Masters of third country fishing vessels or their representatives shall notify the competent authorities of the Member State whose designated port or landing facilities they wish to use at least three working days before the estimated time of arrival at the port"

The regulation states "Fishing vessels" and the three days' notice is based on estimation of steaming time from traditional catching areas to EU harbours. However, reefer vessels are excluded in the regulation!

- Reefer vessels are loading for several days along the coast of Norway, between different loading ports in Iceland and Faroe Islands. Frequently one vessel loads frozen fish for two or three discharging ports and the final destination of cargo will be known in many cases only after departure. Loading operations are mainly completed by Friday evening or Saturday/Sunday.

The reefer vessel will not be allowed to enter a discharging port on the following Monday due to improper notification of 3 working days.

Non-technical measures - Autonomous Tariff Quotas

The EU supply of certain fishery products currently depends on imports from third countries, either because these products are not produced in the EU or because they are not produced in enough

AUTONOMOUS TARIFF QUOTA SYSTEM (ATQ'S) EU REGULATION 2015/2265 FOR 2016-2018

ATQs are assigned to imported raw materials / fishery products, which are meant for further processing in Europe. The ATQs are instruments agreed for a three-year period by the EU and third countries then managed on a first-come first served basis.

ATQs regulate the quantity and as a result the price. ATQs are not given out for countries - fish can come from any country, as long as they qualify for processing. However, there are procedural problems.

- *Importers need to have a guarantee if using the ATQ, which is costly,*
- *New custom rules where the importer is responsible,*
- *The system favours the big players who have finances to keep stock.*

ATQs are perceived by a third country as a barrier and therefore they are pushing for higher quotas.

quantities. ATQ is a potential way to get processing back to EU, where higher technology compensates labour cost. The trend is to move away from frozen fish to fresh fish. There used to be a suspension system, where unlimited amounts could be imported. Today ATQs are limiting because they are exhausted early, so not enough raw material is available for processing, and it is a risk for operators, and leads to gambling with species and competition.

The system before was based on licenses for processors, who were responsible and were checked. The importer was never liable for what would happen later in the chain. Now it has reversed. There is no governance and management of the contracts to the processor. It is not known if they will do what they plan to do, especially when processed in a different country. No

connection and no traceability. Now, if there is a problem the importer is responsible. It is difficult for the importer to have the responsibility because it is hard to follow the products upwards through the chain. Now they can trace back to importer and it is hard to share the responsibility. Importer and processor have to make an agreement to cover the additional cost (customs, food safety etc.).

Keynote lecture on Antidumping and Seafood

ANTI-DUMPING AND SEAFOOD

Anti – dumping procedures are legitimate alternatives to tariffs and a defined NTM.

- Dumping to obtain foreign exchange
- Disruptive for the domestic market
- Predatory pricing to take over
- To determine if dumping has taken place prices are checked
- Subsidies

Ecolabels like Marine Stewardship Council (MSC) may create more challenges than the dumping issue, as developing countries see ecolabels as barriers, since they cannot provide evidence on fishery management

New markets are growing – Europe is trying to improve things but may be losing out in the competition with new markets

Aquaculture products in most markets have increased rapidly enough to warrant the use of safeguard measures, making farmed seafood a main target in trade conflicts with seafood. Aquaculture has made seafood more available and competition from aquaculture has influence on wild fish prices.

More and more difficult to get product in the EU as other markets are growing. One hand improving and working towards a better system globally. Other hand where other markets are growing and products produced elsewhere. Same price or little bit less. Improvement measures but may be losers at the same time because it becomes a barrier

Main impacts: The producers do not get a better price, and they sell to whoever offers the higher price.

- ➔ Will EU have to pay higher price to meet the competition from other markets?
 - ➔ EU and North America impose standards on everyone else and will consumers eventually pay for everything?
 - ➔ Increasingly consumers care about production methods, and sustainability issues.
- WTO maintains that it is fine (OK) as long as you do not discriminate.

World Cafe

World Café discussions highlighted relevant issues for policy, the value chain and markets including the following key topics:

1) Aspects of policy-making and the contents of regulations;

- Implementation of policies
- Private versus public standards

Stakeholders review notes from one of the World Café tables and work towards conclusions

2) Value chain and NTMs, what is needed for value chain actors?

- Technical processes and procedures,
- Certification and labelling,
- Standards,

- Regulation and the value chain,
- Technology in the value chain,
- Trends and future changes.

3) Market trends and global market drivers?

- Global approach,
- Political decisions are making huge effect on the global landscape on market trends;
- Consumers,
- Technical issues and administrative barriers.

World Café discussions and working on NTM issues in Brussels.

Conclusions

The results from the workshop show that technical barriers to trade is the main NTM category where policy could be used to address issues and therefore to improve the trade of seafood. In particular, it was recognised that 'product identity requirements' and 'labelling, marking and packaging' are specific areas that could be addressed. Tariff rate quotas and subsequently SPS measures were also shown to be areas that could be considered by policy.

Furthermore, research undertaken on NTMs in the SUCCESS project was presented earlier at the World Seafood Conference 2017 in Reykjavík¹, Iceland, where efforts have been made to quantify the impacts of NTMs according to the views of stakeholders shows that:

- ⇒ the playing field is not level with regard to trading seafood across EU, and
- ⇒ clear concerns regarding NTMs in EU,
- ⇒ there is a clear importance to verify origin for both imports and exports (customs to consumer),
- ⇒ there is a clear need for standardisation requirements for all EU countries (e.g. SPS, certificates etc.),
- ⇒ there are costs for businesses in navigating non-tariff measures, sometimes it can be a direct cost of losing business or even a shipment, sometimes it's just red tape. Ultimately company reputation is at stake, and risk avoidance creates costs to trade.

More information

More information on the NTM workshop and copies of the slides presented are available on the SUCCESS website, visit this link here:
<http://www.success-h2020.eu/success-workshops/workshop-brussels-2017/>

¹ Simone Mardle et al 2017, http://www.success-h2020.eu/app/download/5811058344/WSC_2017_Presentation_Simon_Mardle-1.pdf

THE SEAFOOD CONFERENCE ICELAND 2017,

Reykjavik, Iceland 16-17 November 2017

A SUCCESS stand was used to showcase the SUCCESS project for the 700 event’s participants, and two presentations of SUCCESS project results to obtain feedback from participants.

30 NOV 2017

SUCCESS STAKEHOLDER WORKSHOP

The Seafood Conference Iceland

16-17 NOVEMBER 2017

H2020 PROJECT "BLUE GROWTH STRATEGY"

H2020 GRANT AGREEMENT NO. 635188

PARTNERS AND STAKEHOLDERS AT THE CONFERENCE

STAKEHOLDER VIEWS ON COMPETITIVENESS & SUSTAINABILITY

Meet us in Harpa

The Success project recently hosted a workshop with key stakeholders to provide first hand-information for Non-Tariff Measures (NTMs) in EU fisheries and aquaculture sector value chains. Both sectors rely on exporting to third countries and importing from third countries. Recent global events and technological developments are potentially changing the trade environment and NTMs are important. The specific aim of the workshop was to identify which NTMs matter and are relevant for the EU fishery/aquaculture sector, and to identify the actual issues at hand to inform and improve EU policy. Furthermore, if possible some cost indication will be retrieved to inform the impact of NTMs on EU public policies. We will be at the SUCCESS project stand during the SUR2017.

Impacts of BREXIT, free trade agreements, and booming shifts in international trade policies affected through Non-Tariff-Measures (NTMs),

1

Harpa Conference Center in Reykjavik

MarkMar team, from left Kristinn, Gudrun, Hildigunnur and Sigurdur

STAKEHOLDERS' PERCEPTION OF SUSTAINABILITY,

On-line survey conducted in November 2017 in connection with the Seafood Conference Iceland - Questionnaire from SUR 2017

ICELANDIC STAKEHOLDERS' PERCEPTIONS OF SUSTAINABLE AND COMPETITIVE SEAFOOD INDUSTRIES (SUCCESS H2020)

On-line survey, November, 2017.

OBJECTIVES

- ✓ To explore the views of Icelandic stakeholders towards the concept sustainability in connection with different seafood industry sectors:
 - i) fisheries,
 - ii) coastal fisheries,
 - iii) aquaculture
- ✓ To assess the perception of stakeholders in Iceland towards key themes influencing competitiveness:
 - "Regulations"
 - "Markets"
 - "Processing & transport"
 - "Seafood Value Chains"
 - "Sustainability"

On-line survey

The overall objective was to assess the perception of Icelandic stakeholders towards the concept sustainability and identify issues that may have an impact on the long term economic sustainability and competitiveness, in particular explore factors which were perceived to influence the Icelandic fisheries and aquaculture sectors.

The questionnaire included both direct and open ended questions and was sent by e-mail with a link to the on-line survey to a selected group of seafood value chain stakeholders in Iceland (approx. 2000). A total of 110 responses were obtained during the last week in November 2017 (response rate~6%).

Main results

Fisheries were considered "sustainable" by higher proportion of the respondents (75%), when compared with results from coastal fisheries (57%) and aquaculture (52%) (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Do you consider ["Fisheries", "Coastal Fisheries", "Aquaculture"] sustainable?

STAKEHOLDERS' PERCEPTIONS TOWARDS SUSTAINABILITY

The majority of stakeholders considered **Icelandic fisheries** to be sustainable as reflected by following statements: "sustainable utilization of stocks which ensures optimal value creation for the future". "Fisheries are based on scientific research and they are controlled efficiently". "There is a common understanding and consensus in the community about these fundamental elements". However, there was awareness that some fish species are overfished.

Coastal fisheries were perceived as less economically profitable, but social and regional impacts were highlighted. The fishing was perceived to be controlled with caution and the fishing rules, restrictions and the framework for coastal fisheries are such that the impact on fish stocks were considered minimal.

It was noted that **aquaculture in Iceland** was a development in the right direction for the future, however concerns were raised regarding environmental impacts. The regulatory framework and standards implemented were acknowledged as follows: "All aspects of aquaculture strongly suggest that it is sustainable." [...] "If managed and operated according to best practices, the farming can be sustainable, but it requires knowledge and caution"

"Control of the chain is of benefit for the marketing and secures the sale of fresh produce" [...] "Market-driven industry, secure delivery and direct relationship with buyers."

"Icelandic fish processing industry is known as economically sustainable and therefore should have a competitive advantage". But there is competition in the market: "the competitors are ahead and they emphasize it in their marketing."

Seafood value chains

VALUE CHAIN GOVERNANCE AND THE INFLUENCE ON COMPETITIVENESS

Vertical integration that allows fish to be managed according to the need of the market was considered important and more efficient, rather than the sole focus on fishing.

"We do not control the value chain all the way to the consumer. The bulk of Icelandic fish is sold to intermediaries in other countries. [...]"

"The value distribution is not level since the processing gets a small part of the value added in the value chain". [...] *"The final price to consumers / customers determines the profitability of the industry".*

[Icelandic stakeholders, Nov 2017]

The ability to control all aspects of the value chain and to be able to respond to demand was considered the key to competitiveness.

"A holistic view of the value chain is a prerequisite for freshness and long-term competitiveness" [...] *"It is important for product quality, production and marketing to manage the value chain from A to Z".*

It was noted that differentiation must be in place and the competitive advantage was perceived as the high level of technology, product development in the fish processing, freshness and secure delivery of quality products.

"I believe that integration of fishing and processing gives a lot of advantage, but it is also a real monopoly that could cause a significant loss to the industry in the long run" [...] *"important to have an overview and cooperation in the whole chain".*

Markets

The drawback for Iceland is the distance from the markets:

"We are further away from the market than, for example, Norwegians."

Icelandic seafood is *"always in competition with products from other nations"*, and many are fighting for the same market: *"Important to ensure the reliability of deliveries throughout the year"* and *"achieve market differentiation"*

Authorities / Regulations

"The regulatory framework is essential, otherwise it is not possible to confirm sustainability"

However, it was stated that, *"the regulatory framework needed to provide much better control and surveillance"* for example surveillance of landings was mentioned. Others perceived that, *"the authorities were too restrictive"* and their view was that *"the regulatory framework was limiting for the sector"*. The view was also expressed that, *"limited access to the fisheries ensures profitability"*, while others emphasised the *"need for separation of fishing and processing"*

Processing and transport

QUALITY AND CONSISTENT DELIVERY

"Rapid processing of raw materials delivers better products and fast transportation between countries guarantee the freshness of products".

"Consistent delivery - security and freshness"
"Quality delivered to the consumer's table"

"Distance from the mainland markets, limits the transportation routes. On the other hand, there are good and fairly diverse possibilities of transport routes in spite of everything" [...]

"It's important to maintain the quality and the quality reputation of the Icelandic seafood products. It is the processing and the unbroken chilled supply chain that matter most"

Sustainability

Key issues are to maintain the sustainability of the stocks for the future. However, it was noted that the definition of the concept "sustainability" was much wider and therefore *"sustainability must be viewed holistically in the context of environmental, social and economic impacts"*.

PERCEPTIONS OF SUSTAINABILITY

"the stocks should be utilised in a responsible way, so we will not eliminate the stock" [...] *"The sustainability of the resource is essential for the long-term competitiveness of the industry."*

"improve efficiency and collaboration in the supply chain from sea to land and to markets".

[Icelandic stakeholders, Nov 2017]

More Information:

The survey was organised by MarkMar as part of stakeholder outreach activity in the SUCCESS project: www.success-h2020.eu; Contact: sigurdur.bogason@markmar.is

The overall report will be available on the University of Iceland ASCS website: www.ascs.is Contact: go@hi.is

REFERENCES

As part of the co-creation activities in WP9 and also to provide a timely broader communication and dissemination outreach, newsletters, summary reports and presentations were made publicly available on the SUCCESS project's website. In addition to the reporting from workshop events, surveys were conducted to gain insights and inputs into stakeholder perceptions on the issues concerning them in relation to the seafood and aquaculture sectors.

Following is a list of WP9 events and the links to the SUCCESS website as well as the citations of the working documents that were created from minutes and synthesis of results in the following WP9 stakeholder workshops. For more information, contact: sigboga@markmar.is

- **World Café “Baseline for competitiveness”, Reykjavík, 12 April 2016**

<http://www.success-h2020.eu/success-workshops/workshop-reykjavik-2016/>

Ólafsdóttir, G., Sigurdardóttir, H. and Bogason S.G. (2016) Competitiveness of Icelandic fisheries and aquaculture products – World Café Reykjavík, April 12, 2016. WP9 Working Document, SUCCESS EU funded H2020 project no. 635188, 43p

- **Focus Group Workshop and World Café, Rome, May 18-19, 2016, “Competitiveness and Sustainable Sourcing in Europe for Fish and Seafood”**

<http://www.success-h2020.eu/success-workshops/workshop-rome-2016/>

Ólafsdóttir, G, Nourry, M., Mardle, S., Rau, M.L., Polonco, J.M.F., Cozzolino, M., Zander, K., Sigurðardóttir, H., LeGallic, B., Bogason S. (2016). Competitiveness and Sustainable Sourcing in Europe for Fish and Seafood, WP9 Working Document SUCCESS H2020 project GA 635188. Focus Group Workshop and World Café, Rome, May 18-19, 2016, 36p

- **Stakeholders' perception analysis, World Café, Santander, May 10-12, 2017. Price Transmission and Market Power in the Seafood Value Chain in Europe**

Ólafsdóttir, G., Le Gallic, B., Cozzolini, M., Gambino, M. Mardle, S., Llorrente, I. , Bogason, S.G. (2017). Stakeholders' perception on PRICE TRANSMISSION AND MARKET POWER IN THE SEAFOOD VALUE CHAIN IN EUROPE. SUCCESS World Café, Santander, WP9 Working Document SUCCESS project. Funded by EC H2020 no. 635188. University of Iceland /MarkMar, 16p.

<http://www.success-h2020.eu/success-workshops/workshop-cantabria-2017/>

- **Slow Fish International event Genova, 18-21 May 2017, focused on the case study on coastal fisheries and included a survey questionnaire**

Ólafsdóttir, G., Daures, F., Malvarosa, L., Sabatella R. F., Paolucci C., Nourry M., Pirrone C., Fazio G., Fricano, S., Le Grel, L., Bogason, S. G. (2017) Stakeholders' perception analysis - Questionnaire and Round table, SUCCESS Co-creation platform and Case Study on Coastal Fisheries. SUCCESS project funded by the European Commission H2020, GA no. 635188, SlowFish International event, Genova, Italy May, 2017. University of Iceland /MarkMar, 31p.

- **Workshop and World Café on NTMs, Brussels, Belgium 10-11 October 2017**

<http://www.success-h2020.eu/success-workshops/workshop-brussels-2017/>

Ólafsdóttir, G., Sigurdardóttir, H., Mardle, S., Rau, M.L., Le Gallic, B., Angulo, L., Bogason, S. (2017). SUCCESS Co-creation platform and NTMs - Report from workshop „Future Trade in Seafood“, Brussels, 10-11 October 2017. SUCCESS project. Funded by EC H2020 no. 635188, University of Iceland /MarkMar, 45p.

- **The Seafood Conference Iceland, 15-16 November 2017, - showcasing SUCCESS project,**
 - *STAKEHOLDERS' PERCEPTION OF SUSTAINABILITY, On-line survey conducted in November 2017 in connection with the Seafood Conference Iceland.*

Olafsdottir, G., Sigurdardottir, H., Bogason S. G. (2018) Icelandic stakeholders' perceptions of sustainable and competitive seafood industries. Working document WP9, SUCCESS project funded by the European Commission H2020, GA no. 635188, University of Iceland /MarkMar,35p.

<http://www.success-h2020.eu/events-conferences/seafood-conference-iceland-2017/>

- **SUCCESS Policy Roadmap – Milestone document**

Bogason, S.G., Olafsdottir, G., Sigurdardottir, H., Lorrente, I, Haraldsson, G.O., Fridriksson, K. (2018). Milestone No. 50, Preparation of a roadmap for implementation of SUCCESS outcomes as perceived by the stakeholders. WP9 Working Document SUCCESS H2020 project GA 635188. University of Iceland/MarkMar. February 28, 2018.

<http://www.success-h2020.eu/events-conferences/world-seafood-congress-2015/>

<http://www.success-h2020.eu/events-conferences/world-seafood-congress-2017/>

ANNEX I – NEWS CLIPPINGS FROM EVENTS

Slow Fish event:

SUCCESS, a European project focused on the economic sustainability of coastal fishing

In evidence

Font Size

May 29th 2017

https://youtu.be/bTk44_sxgnE

The recent trends in coastal fishing trends suggest that the sector is characterized by initiatives aimed at responding to the **increasing demand from consumers for fresh and high quality sustainable products**.

Coastal fisheries are analyzed in the **SUCCESS** project (Strategic Use of Competitiveness towards Consolidating the Economic Sustainability of the European Seafood sector). SUCCESS is a **European research project funded under the EU strategy H2020**, the EU's research and innovation program for the period 2014-2020.

The H2020 focuses on three fundamental themes: the **science of excellence**, **industrial leadership** and **social challenges** and the SUCCESS project has been funded under the theme "**Consolidating the economic sustainability and competitiveness of European fisheries sectors and seize the potential of the market**".

The SUCCESS project is led by a consortium with important partnerships and contributions from stakeholders: 24 academic partners (universities, research centers) and non-academic partners (companies) from 11 EU and non-EU countries, working in the field of European fisheries and aquaculture. The contribution of the stakeholders will make it possible to ensure the project's relevance and direction of research. The project aims to provide scientific support to European producers, to provide the state of the art and the evolutionary perspectives of the value chain of fishery products and to provide reliable and easy-to-use tools for the planning and development of European markets.

During the last edition of **Slowfish**, held in Genoa from 18 to 21 May 2017, on the stand of the SUCCESS project, discussions and round tables were held on the key themes of coastal fishing, with a strong involvement of stakeholders. The main objective was to create an **exchange platform**, **comparing researchers and fishermen** present and discuss initiatives implemented by Italian and European coastal fishermen on the main marketing strategies adopted in selected case studies, aimed at improving the competitiveness and sustainability of coastal fishing activities and verifying the possible replicability of successful initiatives. The discussions were supported by posters and short films made ad hoc.

Here are some facts:

- 12 posters, 5 films presented by the stakeholders who contributed to the project and a team of 10 researchers representing some of the partners of the SUCCESS project (**NISEA**, **UBO**, **IFREMER**, **UNIPA**, **Fishpass** and **Markmar**) who assured, day per day, the presentation of the results;
- The stand welcomed more than 200 visitors during the 4 days (about 100 visited the stand and another 100 gathered general information about the project), coming from different countries, including non-EU countries (USA, Japan but also African countries), institutional, scientific and industrial representatives but also simple citizens who are simply interested, because they are fish consumers and / or worried about sustainability issues.
- A French secondary school class, prepared by teachers on Slowfish topics. They discovered the sea bass fishing activity thanks to the projected film and participated actively and directly in the discussion with the French stakeholder / fisherman.
- The SUCCESS stand was honored by the visit of the European parliamentary Renata Briano, the president of the Slowfish scientific committee (Silvestro Greco), by a delegation from the Sicilian regional administration, by the Italian senator Andrea Cioffi and by many institutional stakeholders, including representatives of LIFE, Low Impact Fishers of Europe (Jerry Percy and Claudia Orlandini).
- The SUCCESS team organized 2 round tables focusing on specific cases related to projected films and a summary, bringing together all interested guests, LIFE representatives, the SUCCESS team and visitors. The discussions mainly concerned the difficulties raised by the management of shared resources between small-scale and large-scale fleets, the complexity of EU policies and the risk of contradictions or misunderstandings in the interpretation of such policies at national, regional or local level.

Eurofish magazine:

[PROJECTS]

Project places hitherto unseen emphasis on coastal fisheries

Finding a formula for Success

Coastal fisheries represent about 70% of the total fisheries in Europe and are the lifeblood of coastal communities, supporting subsistence and livelihoods across the region. However, the continuous decline in income and employment in the sector, caused partly by increased competition with large scale fishing, has made imperative the need for innovative responses that are both sustainable and inclusive.

The Success team at Slowfish in Genova presented more than 200 visitors with case studies and movies on success stories from coastal fisheries across Europe.

Eurofish Magazine visited the “Success” stand at the Slowfish event in Genova to hear about “success stories” from different European countries and how these can be used as models to improve coastal fisheries in other areas.

Consumers willing to pay more

Consumers’ preferences and willingness to pay for fish caught from coastal fisheries was surveyed in eight countries with over 4,000 participants. The study found that the main reasons for preferring local production of fish was greater freshness, followed by support for the local economy, and shorter transport distances. Consumers were apparently also willing

to pay up to 12% more for fish caught from coastal fisheries. Ms Daurès elaborates, “the first results of this broad analysis at European level highlight that there is a significant opportunity for fresh products and for products from local suppliers. Overall, consumers say they are willing to pay a substantial premium, though this varies from country to country – high in Germany and Italy and less in Finland.” Fifteen percent of the consumers termed small scale coastal fisheries an important element of sustainable fisheries.

Additional results on consumer perceptions specifically from France and Italy show that the definition of “coastal fisheries” is not always clear, although most

respondents associate the term with ‘local’. In all cases, the words “coastal fisheries” had positive connotations, including ‘higher sustainability’ (both environmentally and economically), ‘better food experience’ with regards to quality and variety, ‘fresher products’ and ‘greater confidence’ in producers. Some negative connotations relate to environmental issues like pollution and overfishing, but the good far outweigh the bad.

When comparing consumer perceptions in larger cities like Paris with smaller ones along the coast, it is apparent that small coastal cities are much more positively inclined towards coastal fisheries than the large inland cities, where knowledge about coastal fisheries is lacking and where the

term “coastal” is associated more with leisure activities.

A label with a difference

Positive consumer perceptions towards coastal fisheries can be put to good use. In Brittany, France, where fishermen are economically dependent on their sea bass catch, which makes up more than 50% of their revenue. In the nineties, the fishermen faced strong competition from farmed sea bass imports along with growing competition from large scale fishing vessels. This created the need for diversification and the label, “Association des ligneurs de la Pointe de Bretagne,” (Association of liners from Brittany) was created in 1993. Since the label has existed for such a long time it’s success is undeniable with long term statistical evidence.

Sea bass sold by members of the association could charge a substantial higher price than other fishermen. The price premium compared with liners that were not members was about 15% while compared with netters and trawlers it was over 60% per kilo. And the differences in prices increased over time according to data comparisons from 2000 to 2014. “People are confident in our products and know the label signals traditional fishing and guaranteed freshness,” says Ken Kawahara, who represents

[PROJECTS]

The SUCCESS Project
The "Coastal Fisheries" case study

Fabienne DAURES
Research, IFRIMER ANR

The SUCCESS Project

- "Strategic Use of Competitiveness towards Consolidating the Economic Sustainability of the European Seafood Sector"
- Horizon 2020, Duration: 2015-2018
- Objective: Reinforcing the competitiveness of the European fisheries and aquaculture industries
- Interdisciplinary team of 24 partners from all over Europe (economy, marine science, sociology, psychology)

Work Packages

Case Studies

Focus on "Coastal Fish" case studies

Expected impacts

- Consolidation of the economic sustainability of European fisheries and aquaculture sectors (marine and freshwater)
- Scientific support to fishermen and aquaculture producers to better understand and benefit from the functioning of their markets
- Availability of tools for production planning and development of novel products and markets, taking into account trends in the local and global seafood value chain and consumers preferences
- Better understanding of the value chain organization and of prices cycles, including in particular the "boom and bust" cycles, and availability of solutions for predicting and avoiding similar situations in the future
- Boosting the competitiveness of European seafood products by identifying the added value of existing marketing tools and their potential in steering European consumers' choices

IFRIMER, UMR 1008 ANR10
ANR10, the European Union
2015-2018 research and innovation
programme under grant agreement No.
631038

Coastal Fish is only one of several case studies of the Success project and the first time it is addressed on its own in parallel to other species.

the association. These findings demonstrate that it may be useful to implement a simple generic brand for small scale traditional fisheries, something that is currently being considered for implementation at the national level in France, and that perhaps should also be contemplated at the European level.

For more information and other success stories visit the SUCCESS website <http://www.success-h2020.eu> where posters and short movies feature different cases. Or contact Fabienne Daurès on fdaures@ifremer.fr.

Thomas Jensen, thomas.jensen@eurofish.dk

SUCCESS in a nutshell

SUCCESS or "Strategic Use of Competitiveness towards Consolidating the Economic Sustainability of the European Seafood Sector" is a European research project financed over 3 years (2015-2018) and is part

of the H2020 Strategy, an EU Research and Innovation programme that provides funds for a seven year period (2014-2020). The overall aim of the project is to reinforce the competitiveness of the European fisheries and aquaculture industries.

SUCCESS brings together an integrated team of scientists from all fields of fisheries and aquaculture, along with industry partners and key stakeholders. The project consists of different work packages or topics examined from a scientific point of view: consumer preferences; how the different sectors organise themselves in management systems and producer organisations; and the fish trade value chain covering all actors from fishermen to consumers.

The SUCCESS consortium includes 24 academic partners (universities, research centres) and non-academic partners (industrials, firms) from 11 different countries. For more information, visit www.SUCCESS-h2020.eu.

The first workshop on mussel farming hosted by the SUCCESS project in Cattolica, Italy, 27 May 2017

Giuseppe Prioli, President of the European Molluscs Producers Association (EMPA), presented an overview of the European and Italian mussel sector and its main opportunities. In 2014, 450,880 tonnes of mussels were farmed in the EU. Spain is the biggest producer, with 195,375 tonnes, compared to Italy, which produces 63,731 tonnes.

Italian mussel sector faces many obstacles to increase production

Eraldo Rambaldi, Director of the Association of Mediterranean Aquaculture Producers (AMA) elaborated on the main issues currently concerning the mussel sector.

The lack of spatial planning in Italy is one of the main obstacles prohibiting increased production, since mussel farming competes against many other sectors for the space it needs. Another issue is that the local authorities administer the national regulation in different ways that hinder producers, who are working now to get these problems solved. The Italian sector consists of many

small, family-based farmers, who are often former fishermen, so the lack of professionalism and small size are also issues that need to be addressed. Merging into larger units or cooperating to form a consortium of producers under one professional seller are some solutions that would help the sector get more bargaining power over super-markets.

[PROJECTS]

The workshop for stakeholders in the Italian mussel farming industry brought together 40 participants representing 30% of the sector.

A case study from the SUCCESS project was presented by Sophie Girard of France's IFREMER – AMURE Brest. Countries chosen for the study included Spain, Italy, France and the Netherlands as the top four producers in Europe. According to the study, in 2014, about 1,000 people were employed in the Italian mussel sector in 159 companies. The mussel prices indicator for the Netherlands was €1.4 per kilogram compared with €0.73 per kilogram in Italy, and overall, the blue mussels in northern Europe had higher valorisation when compared with the Mediterranean mussels. The costs structure was also presented; one remarkable result was the labour costs distribution among Spain (62%), Italy (39%), France (33%) and the Netherlands (24%), revealing that the industry is more concentrated in a few companies in the north. Future market perspectives foresee increased demand for organic products and new value-added products; however, it was also discussed at the workshop how organically produced mussels do not always fetch higher prices, making the value of investments in organic certification uncertain. The study

mentioned additional bottleneck factors that would restrict the growth of the sector, including the environment (whether natural variations, or other influences causing mussel mortalities or other economic losses resulting from periods of sales closures), the difficulty of obtaining licenses for new sites, the lack of professionalism and organization in the sector's structure, and the ability of some sectors to increase the valorisation of their products through marketing.

Small companies, big potential

Maria Cozzolino from NISEA, an economic research institute specialising in fisheries and aquaculture, also presented an overview of the Italian mussel value chain. One of the main issues discussed at the workshop was the relatively small size of the Italian mussel companies that resulted in limited negotiation power when dealing with supermarkets. The presentation recommended that the Italian sector consider more vertical organization, so it could sell directly to the supermarkets with a much higher valorisation

and profit. Currently, in the French market, 82% of the organic mussels are sold in supermarkets, while in Italy, 65% of mussels is sold in supermarkets from wholesalers.

Ideas for improvement going forward

During the afternoon, the stakeholders were very active in presenting their company's activities and views at the three roundtable discussions. In the workshop, the participants discussed bureaucratic procedures, certification, management, vertical integration and distribution, and room for future improvements.

One main issue discussed was the demand for market access. One producer of oysters had waited three years for the license to produce. By reducing the bureaucratic control, the licensing process could be made speedier. The banks also limited fish farmers, making it hard for them to get loans. The participants would like to have the same conditions for approving loans as the Italian agriculture sector. Moreover, they would like to see farmer

compensations between regions to be made fairer. Currently, those who lose their production due to weather conditions are subjected to compensations regulated by regional authorities that may vary from 0 to 90%. As the workshop concluded, stakeholders walked away with new market information and the opportunity to have expressed and discussed their views in a good atmosphere.

The meeting at Cattolica represented, for the Italian mussel sector, the first official meeting after they formed an association that would represent their needs and protect their interests. The atmosphere was extremely open to research as well as the exchange of professional experiences. Immediate impacts of the meeting have been a greater cohesion among the mussel producers and a higher interest in improving production performance. As a result, interest rates have risen both in the comparison of production costs and in the different value chains in the major mussel producer countries, such as Italy, France, Spain, and even Greece, an emerging producer among the four.